

Concerted European action on Sustainable Applications of REfractories

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Project start date: 01/09/2022. Project duration: 48 months.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no.101072625

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Deliverable D1.4 - Report about the provision (incl. processing) of materials for the different PhDs

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**Funded by
the European Union**

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History of Changes for this Deliverable

Version	Date	Author (Organization)	Inputs / Changes
v 1.00	01/09/2023	Prof. Marc HUGER - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Structure defined
v 1.10	04/09/2023	Mathilda DERENSY - Calderys - Neuwied (DE) Andrea SALERNO - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Kwasi BOATENG - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Molla EWNETE - CNRS PIMM - Paris (FR) Harikeshava RANGANATHAN - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Michiel SMEDES - MUL - Leoben (AT) Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA - BAM - Berlin (DE) Prof. Marc HUGER - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	First version
V1.20	26/02/2024	Mathilda DERENSY - Calderys - Neuwied (DE) Andrea SALERNO - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Kwasi BOATENG - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Molla EWNETE - CNRS PIMM - Paris (FR) Harikeshava RANGANATHAN - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Michiel SMEDES - MUL - Leoben (AT) Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA - BAM - Berlin (DE) Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Revisions Modifications of European logos
V1.30	19/04/2024	Mathilda DERENSY - Calderys - Neuwied (DE) Andrea SALERNO - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Kwasi BOATENG - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Molla EWNETE - CNRS PIMM - Paris (FR) Harikeshava RANGANATHAN - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Michiel SMEDES - MUL - Leoben (AT) Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA - BAM - Berlin (DE) Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Inclusion of section introductions and reordering of some sections.
V1.40	11/09/2024	Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Check of English and formatting
V1.50	05/11/2024	Prof. Marc HUGER - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Check of science, English and formatting
V1.6	21/11/2024	Mathilda DERENSY - Calderys - Neuwied (DE) Andrea SALERNO - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Kwasi BOATENG - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Molla EWNETE - CNRS PIMM - Paris (FR) Harikeshava RANGANATHAN - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Michiel SMEDES - MUL - Leoben (AT) Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA - BAM - Berlin (DE) Prof. Marc HUGER - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Finalisation of section 3
V1.70	20/12/2024	Prof. Marc HUGER - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR) Dr. Glyn DERRICK - CNRS IRCER - Limoges (FR)	Final check

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1 Introduction

Energy intensive industries such as iron and steel, glass, cement and copper operate at high temperatures. During the production process these industries rely on refractory materials to line high temperature vessels such as the steel ladle, float glass baths and tunnel furnaces. As a key enabler of energy intensive industries, even small improvements to refractory materials have the potential to impact the carbon footprint of some of the largest emitters.

Seven of the CESAREF doctoral candidates will be focussed on directly improving the refractory materials as part of the Work Package 2 “Microstructure design for increased sustainability”. Investigation and improvement of the microstructure (which is related to the initial chemical composition and the thermodynamic stability of compounds) at high temperatures is thus one of the key topics to address for the scientific research in the field of refractory materials. Therefore, the first major decision to make is to select for investigation the raw materials (primary and secondary), processing routes, and recipes for pertinent model systems that will have the most significant environmental impact. Starting from an inventory of available primarily and secondary raw materials, arguments will be provided for the selection of those to be investigated in priority with the most valuable processing route and with targeted properties to be evaluated. Based on the elaborated strategy, the work plan organisation will be setup.

2 Inventory of available primary and secondary raw materials

With the environmental impact concern and recent governmental regulations, reducing carbon footprint and waste has become a leitmotif for industries in Europe. In order to achieve a Net-Zero emission of Green House Gas by 2050, according to the European Green Deal, refractory materials (as enablers of energy intensive industries) have a key role to play. The study and optimisation of specific refractory systems will improve their in-service lifetime and in turn, will further reduce the annual demand for refractories. The steel-making industry requires the highest amount of refractory materials with more than 70 % of the global refractories market, more than 30 million tonnes [1].

Generally, refractory products produce carbon emissions in the processing of their raw materials such as calcium aluminate cements and aggregates including high alumina aggregates. The demand for refractories has gradually been decreasing due to process optimisation. For example, 40 years ago, to produce 1 tonne of steel, approximately 30 kg of refractories were needed [2]. Since then, the quantity of refractories required has been progressively reduced to reach approximately 10 kg of refractories per tonne of steel produced.

While the use of high-grade materials and improvements in existing refractory products has led to increased lifetime there is still room for improvement. For example, microstructural design targeted at enhancing thermomechanical properties under in-service conditions can improve the lifetime of refractory products. More recently, a new emphasis on circular based economies has encouraged alternative approaches to extending the lifetime of refractory materials. For example, the use of by-products to replace raw materials.

Within the context just described, the primary and secondary raw refractory materials which could be of interest, within the current context of CESAREF, are discussed in this section. Fundamental information on the properties of each primary or secondary raw material, that will be investigated by the doctoral candidates involved in work package 2, will be presented.

2.1 Alumina and Silica based materials

Refractories in-service are exposed to harsh operating conditions. For example, refractories in steel ladles, where refractory alumina castables/bricks are applied, experience thermal shocks when filled with molten steel. This harsh environment leads to frequent relining and maintenance.

Alumina (Al_2O_3) is one of the most used refractory raw materials due to its chemical stability, high refractoriness and exceptional mechanical properties that make it ideal in high-temperature applications. In addition, alumina has been reported to be a potential raw material in the carbon-neutral transition. Alumina has been found to have excellent stability [3] and exhibit very low permeability [4], [5] to hydrogen atmospheres even at high temperatures.

In general, all alumina raw materials used in refractories come from the Bayer process. In this process, alumina hydrate is extracted and precipitated from ground bauxite using sodium hydroxide [6]. Alumina (aluminium oxide) is finally formed by driving away water from the hydrate in a further step called calcination [6]. From this calcined alumina, further treatments can be applied to obtain different alumina products with specific properties.

Silica (SiO_2) is another raw material commonly used in refractory applications because of its resistance to creep and versatility [7]. Manufacturers can obtain silica-based materials suitable for specific applications by adjusting characteristics such as purity level, crystallinity, and particle size. Silica-rich minerals such as quartz and flint are the source of most silica refractories, whether crystalline or amorphous [8]. Among the silica types employed by the doctoral candidates are microsilica, initially found as a by-product of silicon metal production, and fused silica, a high-purity variant of SiO_2 fused into an amorphous material.

Microsilica (quite easy to produce as small spherical grains of approximately 150 nm) is typically used to improve rheology properties of castables, but by its nature it is not well suited to high temperature applications. On the other hand, calcined alumina is more suited to high temperature applications but the geometry of the grains is usually far from a sphere (not optimal for rheological properties). Quite recently, a new processing route has been developed to generate spherical alumina grains in relatively small sizes, which could allow, at the same time, pertinent rheological properties of castables and suitable behaviour in high temperature applications.

All these materials will be discussed in the following subsections.

2.1.1 Reactive Alumina

Reactive Alumina (RA) is a raw material designed for high-performance refractory materials to fill the gaps between large grains and promote chemical reactions with other components of the recipe. With reactive aluminas, the average particle size (d_{50}) is nearly equal to primary crystals (less than $1\ \mu\text{m}$). To obtain such a product, intensive grinding processes, such as batch dry grinding in a ceramic-lined ball mill with ceramic comminution media, are used to grind calcined alumina until primary single crystals of RA remain. Combining RA with cement and common matrix fines increases the pre-firing strength of low and ultra-low cement castables [9] by filling the smallest gaps between particles. Therefore, less water is required in the mix and rather good flowing properties, at very low water content, are achieved in the castable. As a consequence, higher packing density and less porosity are achieved in the castable which results in high-performance refractory castables.

2.1.2 Tabular Alumina

Tabular and white fused alumina are popular choices for castable/brick preparation and are among the few favourable raw materials used in a wide range of refractory applications. These raw materials are characterised by high refractoriness, chemical stability, high resistance to mechanical wear, rather low thermal conductivity and medium thermal expansion coefficient. As a result, these properties make tabular and white fused alumina-based refractories ideal for the use in high-temperature applications. Metallurgical or medium calcined alumina of high purity are used as the primary raw materials for tabular alumina [10]. Tabular Alumina processing includes forming, drying, sintering and grinding. Tabular Alumina aggregates are produced via a sintering process at temperatures of $1800\ ^\circ\text{C}$ using shaft kilns [11]. The sintered alumina is then cooled and crushed to specific sizes. Tabular Alumina is a high alumina aggregate containing more than 99 % Al_2O_3 .

2.1.3 White fused Alumina

Similar to tabular alumina, metallurgical alumina is used as the raw material for the production of white fused alumina [10]. However, White Fused Alumina (WFA) comes from the fusion of metallurgical alumina in an electric arc furnace at temperatures of around 2100 °C. The microstructures of WFA are influenced by the solidification process. This process involves pouring the melt into large ingots followed by slow cooling, which in turn leads to large corundum crystal formation. This process results in a higher open porosity compared to tabular alumina [10]. The slow cooled, solidified White Fused Alumina is then crushed into aggregates, this results in sharp-edged, large single crystals which are then used in industry [12]. The properties of WFA aggregates have their respective merits in castable applications where, for example, improvements to creep characteristics can be made [13].

As well as WFA, a dense spherical electro-fused alumina, with a completely different microstructure, has recently been developed via a special atomizing and quenching process [12]. This electrofused alumina aggregate is characterised by a combination of spherically shaped particles with a closed microporosity and a polycrystalline structure [12]. The spherical shape, in combination with the properties of corundum, can result in very tough mechanical performance [12]. This product is currently only available at the laboratory scale and is not commercially available. Further understanding of its performance and development for potential use in refractories is required.

It is important to note, the present state of the art on white fused alumina (with varieties in structure, shape and grain size in combination with calcium aluminate binder systems) can offer similar thermomechanical properties in comparison to tabular alumina [12], [13]. Additionally, 2000-3000 kWh of electric power per tonne of WFA produced is consumed during production. This makes electrofusion an energy intensive process, which is approximately three times higher than that of sintered tabular alumina. The production of sintered tabular alumina, however, uses natural gas as the heat source adding to carbon emissions. White fused alumina, on the other hand, has the potential to use green electricity, generated in Europe, as the power source for fusion. This would be a great step towards carbon neutrality in the industry.

2.1.4 Microsilica

Microsilica is an ultrafine, amorphous powder composed of perfectly spherical silicon dioxide (SiO₂) particles with an average particle diameter of 150 nm. Microsilica was initially a by-product of the smelting process, which involves burning coal and high-purity quartz in electric furnaces to create silicon and ferrosilicon alloys. Due to their amorphous structure and high specific areas (20 m²/g), these ultrafine particles contribute to improving particle packing, as well as also being beneficial to various applications, such as improved sintering capabilities and improved high temperature performance in refractory materials. As a result, microsilica powder is widely used in refractory technology as an additive and binding agent [14]. Based on purity level (85-99 %), microsilica can be found in different grades. The high purity of Elkem Microsilica (ELKEM MICROSILICA® 971), for example, can have a significant impact on the quality of refractory castables, in particular bonding phases at elevated temperatures. It is also used in developing dense refractory castables including low cement bonded castables, ultra-low-cement bonded castables, and non-cement bonded castables.

2.1.5 Fused silica

Fused silica is a high-purity glass variant of SiO₂ and it serves as a primary raw material in refractories for various high-temperature thermal processes, including steelmaking, investment casting and glass manufacture. One of the most attractive properties of this material is its unusually low coefficient of thermal expansion (approximately $0.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$), resulting in an outstanding thermal shock resistance [15]. These properties make fused silica an excellent material for applications demanding exceptional dimensional stability over a wide temperature range. Moreover, it is also

chemically inert to most elements and compounds, except to hydrofluoric acid and strongly alkaline solutions, which dissolve silica [16]. The principal processing route of fused silica is electric fusion, which consists of melting quartz at very high temperatures (approximately 2200 °C) with an electric current in a resistance-heated furnace [17]. The silica melt is then solidified after cooling, forming a solid mass of glass [18]. Although fused silica has good thermal and chemical properties, at temperatures above 1100 °C, it might locally devitrify into a phase called cristobalite, which can lead to shrinkage and microcracking formation [19], [20]. This phase transformation, also known as the crystallization of fused silica, is influenced by several factors, such as impurities and particle size distribution [21], [22]. Therefore, the crystallization of fused silica requires further investigation to maintain the high-temperature properties of silica-based refractories.

2.1.6 AloxX-Spheres

AloxX-Spheres™ (polycrystal alumina) are spherical alumina particles produced in a proprietary process, which are known for their high packing density, high purity, high sintering capabilities and high solid concentration without dilatancy [24]. In addition to sintering agents for high-alumina applications, the AloxX-Sphere particles are also used in the formation of spinel and high-temperature toughening applications. Internal tests at Elkem show that replacing the traditional reactive and calcined (platelets shape) alumina particles by these novel spherical particles favours the self-flow and shortens wet-out time (period of time takes castables to become homogeneously wet) [23]. This polycrystalline alumina needs further investigation to better understand what phases are present within it and how the crystal structure affects reactivity of sintering at high temperature.

2.2 Other materials

2.2.1 Calcium aluminate cement

Calcium aluminate cement (CAC) is a binder used in the creation of unshaped refractories. This binder experiences a hydration reaction, resulting in fast setting, a high green strength and chemical stability. Calcium aluminates are obtained by a high temperature reaction between lime and alumina, resulting in coarse calcium aluminate lumps called clinkers. These clinkers can then be ground down into a powder and used as either an aggregate or a binder. Calcia (C) alumina (A) components with ratios CA and CA₂ have lower melting points compared to CA₆. This has given rise to CAC with high alumina contents of up to 80 wt % for high temperature applications [24]. A large drawback for the use of CAC in high temperature applications is its reaction with the commonly added silica. Due to the tendency of both calcia and silica to gather at the grain boundaries, the increased concentrations of calcia and silica form a low melting point glassy phase. This glassy phase can be detrimental for the refractoriness of the ceramic due to the lubrication effect it has on the aggregates [25].

2.2.2 Vanadium slag

To control the final composition of steel, various impurities from the hot metal need to be removed. This is achieved through a refining process, which uses lime under oxidizing conditions, where carbon, silicon, manganese, vanadium, sulfur and phosphorous are either oxidized to gases or passed into the slag [26]. The slag is extracted from the steel furnace and poured into slag banks to solidify into a crystalline form. Then it can be crushed into different sizes from larger blocks to fine powders. Producing one ton of steel in an integrated steel plant generates about half a ton of by-products, slags (90 % by mass), dusts and sludges [27]. Vanadium is found in metallurgical slags, which are widely distributed around the world. As a by-product, vanadium slag accounts for more than 60 % of the world's overall vanadium production [28]. Depending on the steel production route, different types of slags are produced with different compositions. In one study, the vanadium slag is removed from a basic oxygen furnace. The significant amount of lime (CaO), alumina (Al₂O₃) and magnesia

(MgO) make it suitable for use as a secondary raw material in refractories formulations for lining applications. It can be seen as a bonding agent, with similar properties as calcium aluminate cement, in terms of hardening and setting properties when mixed with an activator [26]. Slag composition and its ability to form hydrates are the main parameters that affect the feasibility of slag usage as a cement. Compared with CAC cement, using slag is more environmentally friendly, reduces the usage of virgin natural raw materials and reduces costs related to their extraction and processing. Enhancing the replacement of conventional raw materials with industrial by-products present environmental advantages crucial for advancing towards climate neutrality within the European Green Deal framework. The vanadium content in the slag depends on the molten steel and the technologies used for steelmaking process. For the CESAREF project, the vanadium content in the slag is less than 2 wt. %. The vanadium does not notably contribute to enhance the properties of the castables.

2.2.3 Magnesias

In the context of refractory materials based on magnesium oxide, different wording can be used: MgO, magnesias, periclase and magnesite. Technically, MgO is the chemical formula for magnesium oxide, also identified as magnesias, whose cubic crystalline form takes the name periclase. The term magnesite, on the other hand, refers to the mineral name of the magnesium carbonate (MgCO₃) which is the predominant raw material from which MgO is obtained. The American Society for Testing of Materials (ASTM) defines a magnesias refractory as “a dead-burned refractory material consisting predominantly of crystalline magnesium oxide” [29]. The term “dead-burned” is intended to indicate a material resulting from an intensive heat treatment giving rise to a certain product resistant to atmospheric hydration and recombination with carbon dioxide (CO₂) [30]. Thus, it is evident that to produce a magnesias refractory product, a heating process is requested. Magnesite accounts for more than the 80 % of the primary raw material to produce refractory grade magnesias [31]. Other sources are seawater, inland brines, or salt deposits [1], [32], [33], [34]. Despite the high purity of MgO that can be extracted from these alternative sources, low yields as well as the often complicated and energy intensive processes required for the MgO extraction, impede their usage [33].

Roughly 30 million metric tons of magnesite are produced every year with China accounting for more than the 65 % of the total [1]. The need for the magnesite heat treatment to obtain the suited grade of magnesias, is related to the release of carbon component following the chemical reaction:

Theoretically, nearly 48 wt. % of magnesite is composed of MgO, so roughly half the weight of the raw material is lost during the reaction [34]. The production of magnesias refractories has thus, inevitably, a high CO₂ footprint. Additionally, the impurities (type and concentration) present in the final magnesias, defining its grade, are strictly related to the thermal process to which the raw material has been subjected. Hence, it is possible to list magnesias based on the heat treatment received. From the lowest to the highest temperatures involved during the magnesite decomposition: caustic calcined magnesias (CCM), dead-burned magnesias (DBM), and fused magnesias (FM). Caustic calcined magnesias, the lowest grade, involves crude magnesite treatment at relatively low temperatures, between 900 and 1300 °C. It is estimated that for 1 ton of CCM 2 tons of magnesite are needed and roughly 2 tons of CO₂ is generated during the process [35]. Dead-burned magnesias, high grade, involves magnesite being sinter-burned at temperatures ranging from 1500 to over 2200 °C. The DBM production involves roughly 2.1 tons of raw material per ton of DBM and generates 2.4 tons of CO₂ [35]. Concerning fused magnesias, the highest grade, magnesite is melted in electric arc furnaces at temperatures exceeding the melting point of MgO, 2852 °C. CCM is commonly used as the melting material to produce FM and roughly 1.5 tons of it are necessary per ton of FM obtained, this leads to a rough estimation of 3 tons of CO₂ produced over the complete process [35].

As just said, magnesias has a very high melting point, above 2800 °C, and together with its resistance to basic slags, moderate cost, makes magnesias products the choice for heat-intensive, metallurgical processes such as for the production of metals and cements [36]. However, magnesias-

based refractories have few disadvantages, such as high thermal expansion coefficient, poor thermal shock resistance and hydration tendency [30], [37]. To improve these performances, many refractories based on MgO are combined with other materials such as alumina, spinel, chromia and carbon.

2.2.4 Forsterite

Forsterite is a magnesium silicate mineral phase of the olivine solid solution with formula Mg_2SiO_4 and atomic structure composed of SiO_2 tetrahedra and MgO octahedra with alternate orientations. It is particularly known for its high melting point, above 1700 °C, low conductivity values and good mechanical resistance [30]. These properties allow it to be a good candidate for mixing with vermiculate to produce insulating refractory materials. Indeed, in the field of refractory materials for steel making, vermiculite-based materials are commonly used as an insulation lining for liquid steel vessels to prevent energy losses, in other words, not being in direct contact with molten steel. However, steel making applications do not require only insulation properties, but also high temperature stability and mechanical resistance. Hence, forsterite is commonly mixed with vermiculite, an appropriate binder and other additives to increase thermal stability and mechanical properties of the final material [36]. Furthermore, to take advantage of its mechanical properties, high melting temperature and low conductivity, Forsterite has been recently added as principal aggregate in monolithic refractories used directly in contact with molten steel. In this case, it acts as sacrificial layer inside the tundish for continuous casting.

2.2.5 Vermiculite

Vermiculite is a mineral which possesses a stable, layered structure of atoms (Figure 1a). Between each atomic layer, exchangeable hydrated ionic species are present [30]. The composition can vary widely depending on the geological conditions and environment in which the mineral was formed, but generally it contains magnesium, aluminium, iron and silicon oxides. Thus, the general chemical formula of vermiculite can be written as $(Mg,Fe,Al)_3((Al,Si)_4O_{10})(OH)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ [38]. When heated to high temperature, the structure loses the interlayer water and a reorganization of the atomic bonds occurs which gives rise to a huge expansion of the structure transversal to the direction of the lamellar atomic planes. For this reason, the thermally treated vermiculite is also called expanded vermiculite, the expansion after heat treatment can reach more than 10 times the initial volume (Figure 1b) [39]. Thus, the final material is a lightweight highly porous material with poor mechanical strength and abrasion resistance making it suitable for insulation applications.

Figure 1: a) octahedral and b) tetrahedral coordinated cation layers of vermiculite with Mg (green), O (red), Si (orange), Al (pink), and H atoms (white) and c) vermiculite before (left) and after thermal expansion (right) [40].

2.2.6 Andalusite/Mullite

Andalusite is a well-known aggregate composed of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 . Andalusite possesses outstanding high temperature volume stability, mechanical strength, thermal shock resistance and creep resistance. Refractories containing such aggregates have been employed in a variety of industrial applications, including the metallurgical industry, steel industries etc. [41].

Andalusite is anisotropic in nature, however, at the application temperature of $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and above, a phase transformation to a mullite phase occurs [41]. Andalusite has an orthorhombic crystalline structure with the dimensional parameters $a \neq b \neq c$ and angular parameters holding the relationship $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$. The mullite phase has the same type of orthorhombic crystalline structure as that of andalusite, the key difference between the two is the interchanged a and b axis due to its topotactic nature. This interchange preserves the anisotropic behaviour in the mullite aggregate after the phase transformation [41].

This anisotropic behaviour makes the microstructure design of andalusite suitable for investigating the thermal shock resistance as a model material for DEM simulations.

3 Synthetic table of potentially interesting primary or secondary raw materials

Raw materials	Primary/ Secondary	Use in the refractory industry	Advantages	Disadvantages	Comment
Reactive Alumina	Primary	Applied as a binder in refractory castables across most energy-intensive industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good thermal stability - Improve flowability - Reduces water demand - Increase pre-firing / green strength of castables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy intensive grinding processes required to achieve the small grain size 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used as a binder in alumina-based systems
Tabular Alumina	Primary	Applied as an aggregate in refractory castables across most energy-intensive industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good corrosion resistance - Intrinsically contains closed porosity suitable for thermal shock applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited abrasion resistance in comparison with white fused alumina 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CO₂ emissions, natural gas used as the power source in production
White fused Alumina	Primary	Applied as an aggregate in refractory castables across most energy-intensive industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wide range of grain sizes available for specific applications - Good wear / abrasion resistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher porosities compared to tabular alumina - Energy-intensive production process - High cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emissions can be reduced through the use of green electricity
Micro-silica (Round sub-micronic grains)	Primary	As a binder in refractory applications (steel and foundry, cement, glass and ceramics)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good workability (setting and hardening time) - Ensure efficient particle packing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy intensive production process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used as a binder in alumina silicate-based systems
Fused silica (Grains in the 1-100 micron range)	Primary	Aerospace and defence as ceramic cores as well as steel production and glassmaking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low thermal expansion over a wide temperature range resulting in high dimensional stability of moulds for casting - High thermal shock resistance - Easily removed with caustic solutions in the case of ceramic cores - Fusion can be conducted using green electricity - Silica is abundant and widely available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electric fusion is highly energy-intensive - Waste disposal of caustic solutions used to remove silica-based ceramic cores 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fused silica is the main material of ceramic cores, which are tools used in the casting of turbine blades in aircraft engines. - Ceramic cores must be removed after casting to leave behind the desired shape or cavity in the final product.
Alox – Spheres (Spherical alumina particles)	Primary	Not currently commercially available. Potential application as a binder in refractory castables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offer excellent particle packing - High refractoriness - Resistant to higher temperatures than fused silica (> 1700 °C) - Reduces dilatancy in comparison to reactive alumina. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High cost - In the case of ceramic cores, it is more difficult to remove after casting when compared with fused silica 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential to be used to tailor the rheology of alumina-spinel refractories.

Calcium aluminate cement	Primary	As a binder in refractory applications (steel and foundry, cement, glass and ceramics)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Excellent hydraulic properties - High thermal stability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production is highly energy-intensive, CO₂ emissions 	
Vanadium slag	Secondary - From the steel industry	Potential application as a binder in refractory castables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Replaces CAC, reducing CO₂ - Reducing use of virgin raw materials - Reducing disposal and associated costs - Locally sourced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential leaching of vanadium during high-temperature conditions, a potential environmental risk - Reduced hydraulic properties in comparison to CAC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling of metallurgical by-products
Magnesia	Secondary	Primary material used in extensive range of refractory products from monolithics to bricks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High corrosion resistance to basic slag - Relatively cheap and abundant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extraction requires a large amount of water and energy - Calcination generates large amounts of CO₂ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investigating the recycling of monolithic tundish working linings is ongoing. This will avoid the initial CO₂ production from the raw materials
Forsterite	Primary, or, Secondary - from a closed loop (Magnesia)	Used mostly as filler for basic refractories and slag conditioners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good additive when used in combination with MgO - High melting point - Low thermal conductivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-quality material is required for use in refractory applications - Low iron-containing primary resources are scarce and relatively expensive - With silica tends to form low melting phases such as enstatite 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The presence of Iron causes low melting phases.
Vermiculite	Primary	Main constituent of insulation lining refractories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Naturally good material for insulation due to layered microstructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fragile - Maximum working temperature of 600 °C - Typical presence of alkaline elements (potassium, sodium, calcium) which can give rise to low melting phases 	
Andalusite	Primary	A wide range of high temperature industries (foundries, steel, cement, glass and aluminium)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can be used directly after mining with minimal processing - Transformation to mullite involves an increase in volume which can compensate for shrinkage of other refractory materials - Lower cost compared to synthetic alternatives. - Very high thermal shock resistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited high temperature performance, decomposes into mullite and silica at 1350 °C. - High water usage and wastewater generation during processing depending on the ore quality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly anisotropic which is beneficial in enhancing the thermal shock resistance of refractories. - Lower carbon emissions in production

4 Refractory materials to be investigated by each DC of WP2

Taking into consideration the material properties, mentioned in the previous section, the choice of materials to be investigated by each doctoral candidate will be discussed here. For each DC the following points will be discussed:

- 1 - The global purpose of each given PhD;
- 2 - The specific interest of each selected primarily or secondary raw materials;
- 3 - The most valuable processing route;
- 4 - The targeted properties to be evaluated.

4.1 PhD04 of Mathilda DERENSY - Use of metallurgical residues as potential raw materials for high performance refractory castables

Remodelling the processing route of refractory materials used for steelmaking could support the decarbonization of the steel industry. The steelmaking industry generates several by-products and wastes during the different stages of steel production. Using secondary resources improves the usage of natural raw materials, reduces costs related to their extraction and processing and as such is better for the environment. PhD04 aims to use the large quantity of vanadium slag by-product to improve the near zero-waste targets. This will be achieved through the transfer of vanadium slag into high-alumina refractory castable formulations to obtain high-performance refractory castables.

The demand for vanadium in the world has grown steadily for the last decade. Since the European Union registered vanadium on the list of Critical Raw Materials in 2017, it has become in Europe's general interest to collect and trade its own vanadium to compete in the market currently dominated by China [42]. A parallel study in the PhD04 Individual Research Project (IRP) proposes advanced and environmentally friendly vanadium extraction from metallurgical residues.

The PhD04 IRP focuses on high alumina refractory castables. Refractory castables involve a dry mix mainly composed of aggregates, a binder phase and additives, and a liquid addition, usually water. Typical aggregates used within the PhD04 IRP are made of tabular alumina with different sizes of particles, from 0.045 - 3 mm. Due to the higher sinter reactivity of tabular alumina (TA), castables containing TA display much higher density and better mechanical properties than castables containing white fused alumina (WFA) [43]. TA with higher purity than WFA is considered for the study. Reactive Alumina and tabular alumina of 0 - 0.045 mm grain sizes are employed as fine aggregates in the formulation. Using different sizes of particles controls the particle size distribution and optimizes the castable's packing and density. The better the packing, the less binder is required in the formulation. As a binder, calcium aluminate cement (CAC) is well-known in the refractory industry. For the last few decades, industries have tended to decrease the usage of CAC because of the energy-intensive process and the release of carbon dioxide to the environment [44]. Despite its colossal carbon footprint (responsible for about 7 % of CO₂ emissions globally [45]), it can be a judicious choice as a reference material.

Dealing with vanadium slag recycling into high-alumina refractory castables is the main objective of the PhD04. Therefore, different vanadium slags with variations in composition are employed to enlarge the panel of results and propose a relevant formulation of castables, containing vanadium slag, while respecting the required properties for industrial applications. To reduce the amount of waste, vanadium slag is introduced either as a bonding phase or as aggregates in the formulation while keeping the required properties to withstand harsh conditions faced in industries.

Many techniques have been developed to effectively recover vanadium from the vanadium slag. The most common process used to extract the vanadium is sodium roasting (usually NaCl, Na₂CO₃ and Na₂SO₄) followed by sulphuric acid or water leaching. However, some concerns about damage to the environment remain, such as emissions of corrosive gases (Cl₂, HCl, SO₂, and SO₃) due to the

decomposition of sodium salts during roasting [46]. New, environmentally friendly, processes for vanadium extraction are under investigation in the PhD04 IRP. These processes feature roasting without the addition of salt [47].

To ensure excellent mechanical properties in real conditions of the refractory materials containing vanadium slag, the study deals with the assessment of its thermomechanical behaviour. For that purpose, microstructural examination of the castables produced is investigated at different working temperatures up to 1500 °C. The method is to examine the phases resulting from different reactions that occurred during casting, drying, or sintering in castables produced with vanadium slag. This project interrogates the impact of the vanadium slag on the microstructure of castables while also focusing on the impact on the mechanical properties at room and high temperatures. Mechanical tests such as cold crushing strength, modulus of rupture, and resonant frequency damping analysis are measured. In the meantime, the project focuses on finding a sustainable way to extract the vanadium from the slag. To do so, advanced experiments with minimum carbon footprint will be developed.

4.2 PhD05 of Andrea SALERNO - Characterization of refractory material properties after usage for recyclability determination

Operative lifetimes of refractories range from hours to several months depending on their role. As a result of increasingly tightening policies, rising disposal costs, and recent supply chain shortages, the recovery and recycling practices of end-of-life refractories are receiving great attention. Reduction of open-loop and down scaling strategies, to maintain refractory materials value as long as possible, are some of the core requirements for sustainability and circularity. To help achieve these objectives, the application of numerical models has proved to be a useful strategy for researchers facing in-use issues related to refractory materials. In this IRP, finite element analysis (FEA) will be applied to end-use refractories in order to understand the suitability, for potential recyclability, of the lining materials from the tundish. Coupled with numerical simulations the experimental characterization of fresh and post-use materials will aim to identify the critical issues related to the continuous casting operations. The comparison between empirical results and appropriate finite elements models (FEM) can potentially identify suitable pathways to improve the refractories sustainability, focussing on damage prevention and reuse of used refractories. Additionally, multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA) strategies help to define the most convenient decisions in circumstances where conflicting parameters are involved. Thus, PhD05 aims to identify suitable parameters for end-of-life lining materials to establish the most convenient route in terms of recycling with a focus on closed-loop practices based on product composition, recycling processes sustainability, and other indicators.

4.3 PhD06 of Kwasi BOATENG - Microstructure design of refractory castables for in use thermomechanical properties optimization

In this project, different kinds of alumina-spinel refractory castables will be considered with the variation in the type of alumina aggregate used; tabular alumina or white fused alumina. Pores and cracks can be classified as almost permanent structural elements in all refractory materials. As such, pores and cracks may have either positive or negative effects on various properties of refractory castables. It has been well established that reduced brittleness in refractories can be achieved by the formation of a pre-designed microcrack network in its microstructure. In addition, the thermal shock resistance of refractories is associated with the presence of microcracks due to the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch between aggregates and matrix, or by the volume expansion caused by phase transformation forming suitable microcracks in refractories [48]. The main aim of this project is to propose a new design for the microstructure of refractory materials with improved thermo-mechanical properties with a special focus on optimizing thermal shock resistance. Firstly, microcracks will be induced in the castables via the differences in the CTE between the alumina aggregates and the spinel as well as the matrix. Secondly, there will be the formation of calcium aluminate phases at high temperatures accompanied by volume expansion. Here, the effects of the

reactivity, crystallinity and aggregate shape and size of both alumina aggregates, on forming favourable microcracks in the castables will be investigated.

In order to achieve a Net-Zero emission of Green House Gas by 2050, according to the European Green Deal, the study and optimisation of specific refractory systems comprising of alumina grains, will be key in the quest to improve their in-service lifetime. In addition, while white fused alumina is produced in a high energy process, it has the potential to be fused using green electricity produced in Europe (Austria, Germany). This, combined with the fact that white fused alumina has excellent refractory properties in comparison to tabular alumina, is why WFA will be investigated in this project. Furthermore, the extent to which the thermal shock resistance can be optimized through microstructural fine-tuning will be investigated.

4.4 PhD07 of Molla EWNETE - Microstructure dependence of local strain through in-situ micromechanical investigations

PhD07 is primarily concerned with investigating different microstructural design features for refractory materials. This will improve refractory materials' performance in steel ladle linings and contribute to environmental sustainability.

This project focuses on various refractory castables, especially alumina-castables (alumina-spinel and mullite). The first part focuses mainly on designing alumina-spinel castables using a calcium alumina binder (CAC) for ladle applications. A cement-bonded alumina spine castable will be designed using both irregular reactive alumina (CL370) and spherical alumina (AloxX-Spheres). Alternative non-cement castables with spinel or without spinel formation will also be developed to replace the cement binder. This is of interest as the properties of the cement binder degrade at high temperatures due to the presence of CaO [49]. For a better understanding of sintering and reactivity, in-situ characterization will be performed on the starting powder materials (Microsilica, AloxX-Spheres, reactive alumina).

Microsilica is commonly used as a reactive filler in refractory castables and it is also used as a non-cement binder, providing the desired setting through coagulation bonds. Although microsilica allows better flowability, optimizes hydration, and ensures good bonding in non-cement bonded castables, it requires an enormous amount of electrical energy (11-13 kWh per kilogram of silicon produced) [50]. When considering the energy needed to produce 1 ton of microsilica or cement, the consumption will vary greatly depending on factors such as the production process and the materials used. In order to produce cement in dry process, approximately 110 kWh are required per ton. Thus, it is important to note that actual energy consumption varies depending on factors like energy efficiency and fuel type (coal, natural gas, alternative fuels) [51].

The thermo-mechanical behaviour of refractory materials is largely based on materials microstructure, including morphology evolution, microcrack network and liquid formations arising during thermal loading. During this project, PhD07 will investigate the thermal behaviour of alumina-based refractory castables by measuring thermal shock resistance using scale transition approaches.

4.5 PhD08 of Harikeshava RANGANATHAN - Discrete Element Method to support microstructure design of refractories

Past research has shown a strong relationship between the microstructure design and the thermomechanical properties of refractory materials [52]. Improvement in the heterogeneity of the materials improves the thermal shock resistance of the material [52], [53]. Asadi [53] and Nguyen [54] employed the advanced numerical technique Discrete Element Method (DEM) to study the influences of the heterogeneity on the thermomechanical properties of refractory materials. This IRP will continue to investigate this relationship using DEM, which will help develop a virtual lab to perform thermomechanical characterisation and to study the influences of the adopted microstructure design on the thermal shock resistance.

Thermal shock resistance of refractory materials has been improved by nucleation of microcracks due to the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) mismatch in the microstructure [53], [54].

Microcrack nucleation in the microstructure leads to quasi-brittle behaviour, influenced by the temperature of the thermal cycle, weight percentage of aggregate present in the sample and anisotropic-isotropic interactions, resulting in non-linear mechanical behaviour [41]. PhD08 will investigate the impact of anisotropic-isotropic interactions on thermal damage nucleation in model materials, highlighting the increased likelihood of matrix-aggregate interaction under thermal expansion. This analysis will be carried out through the input of experimental data, generated in IRP06, into the DEM virtual lab. Here a thermomechanical simulation is performed, by assuming a microstructure design, the output of the simulation will provide insights into the thermal shock resistance of the microstructure. The model materials used in this work will be alumina, andalusite/mullite and/or alumina–aluminium titanate.

This IRP is focused on performing virtual thermomechanical characterisation and the monitoring the evolution of the mechanical and thermal properties under an assumed thermomechanical loading cycle [53], [54]. The DEM virtual lab being developed in this project is based on GranOO on which new features such as periodic boundary conditions, anisotropic thermal expansion and post-processing features will be incorporated, tested and validated. This will help investigate refractory microstructure designs that involve brittle to quasi-brittle behaviour under thermal cycling. It is important to note that DEM virtual lab does not perform or take in to account any phase transformations in the microstructure and the micro-structure is assumed to be chemically inert.

4.6 PhD09 of Michiel SMEDES - Influence of microstructure of refractory materials on the macroscopic mechanical behaviour

In the aerospace industry, a desire for more efficient and greener engines has led to the creation of more complex designs, requiring more complex turbine blades. These turbine blades are conventionally cast by an investment casting method where a ceramic slurry is used to copy all the intricate details of the turbine blade in order to form a shell mould, later to be used to cast new turbine blades. It is essential to understand the relationship between the ingredients in this ceramic slurry and their eventual thermomechanical properties, to design a ceramic that can withstand the molten metal casting of the turbine blades. A multitude of ceramic recipes will be created in this project that can be shaped by casting. A heat profile, normally experienced by the investment casting shell, will be applied to these ceramic castables after which the thermomechanical properties can be evaluated in relation to the materials and microstructure present.

The raw materials used in these ceramic recipes include fumed silica, tabular alumina, fused mullite and CAC. The main requirement for the ceramic shell is thermal stability. The material best suited for thermal stability is mullite, due to a combination of its thermal properties and morphology. This thermal stability is achieved by designing the recipes around primary mullite and optimizing for secondary mullite formation. Silica is added for its capabilities as a binder and to form secondary mullite. The other part of mullite, alumina, is also added in the form of fine sintered alumina powder. Finally, calcium aluminate cement can be added to further improve coagulation and binding effects in the castable.

The chosen materials are selected for high purity as impurities such as alkaline oxides have detrimental effects on the thermal stability of the final ceramic product. Thermal stability can be divided into two key components. The first is a good creep resistance, the ceramic should not deform under the load of the molten metal during casting. The second component is that during heating, the shell should expand or contract in a predictable manner. While a material will expand almost linear with heating, the material might also undergo phase changes, which often go paired with a sudden expansion or contraction.

4.7 PhD10 of Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA - Microstructural impact on refractory materials during In-Situ testing by means of X-ray imaging methods

Another crucial component for producing more sustainable aircraft engines is the ceramic core, which forms complex cavities in the turbine blades during investment casting. Besides reducing engine weight, these cavities also enhance the ability of the turbine blades to withstand high temperatures by creating intricate cooling passages. Nevertheless, the ceramic cores undergo significant microstructural changes during the casting of the blades which can degrade their properties. Therefore, this project focuses on understanding the microstructure-property relationship of ceramic cores via X-ray imaging methods, particularly advanced characterisation techniques such as synchrotron X-ray computed tomography, which researchers have scarcely explored to refractory materials.

The primary raw material chosen for the ceramic cores is fused silica, produced by melting quartz via electrical fusion. Although several studies have employed materials such as alumina, magnesia, and calcia as main components for ceramic cores, fused silica is still the material that presents the best compromise between high-temperature properties and leachability (the ability to remove the core after casting without damaging the turbine [55], [56]). However, fused silica crystallises at casting temperatures, and this phase transformation induces microstructural changes that severely affect the performance of the cores [19], [20]. Thus, it is essential to investigate the microstructural evolution of ceramics under casting conditions to design more efficient aircraft engines.

The targeted properties for evaluating ceramic cores in investment casting include mechanical strength, dimensional stability, and open porosity, which is necessary for effectively removing the core after casting. Synchrotron tomography allows for three-dimensional observations of microstructural changes, which include phenomena like crack propagation, pore network development and particle packing. These observations provide valuable insights into how ceramics behave under different temperatures or applied loads during operation [57], [58], [59]. There are ongoing challenges involving synchrotron experiments, such as sample sizing and movement and the thermal stability of the equipment [60]. However, this work presents a valuable opportunity to enhance the practical application of advanced characterisation methods in the refractory field.

5 Synthetic table on refractory materials to be investigated by each PhD of WP2

PhD	Name	Beneficiaries	Refractory material to be investigated Priority 1	Refractory material to be investigated Priority 2	Refractory material to be investigated Priority 3
4	Mathilda DERENSY	RWTH/Calderys	Raw Materials: Vanadium slag Processing Route: Basic Oxygen Furnace slag cooled down and crushed into powder <63µm Main Objective: Recycling into castables, reducing waste and reducing costs related to raw materials extraction	Raw Materials: Tabular Alumina Processing Route: Sintered α-corundum crystals (Al ₂ O ₃) Main Objective: Used as aggregates and fines in refractory castables	Raw Materials: CAC Processing Route: Fusion of precursor materials (Lime from Limestone and Bauxite) Main Objective: Used as a binder in refractory castables as a reference for comparison with vanadium slag
5	Andrea SALERNO	IRCER/Vesuvius	Raw Materials: Forsterite Processing Route: Mafic minerals containing several solid solutions of olivine minerals, calcined and produced the mineralogical grade Main Objective: Establish a feasible and profitable recycling route	Raw Materials: Alumina-based castable Processing Route: Mining of the kaolinic clay or bauxite ore and mixing with cement & water Main Objective: Define the critical properties inducing in-service ageing and define the potential recyclability	Raw Materials: Vermiculite Processing Route: South Africa mining from mica ores, hydrated and finally exfoliated Main Objective: Define the critical properties inducing in-service ageing and define the potential recyclability
6	Kwasi BOATENG	IRCER/Imerys	Raw Materials: White Fused Alumina Processing Route: Fusion in an electric arc furnace. Main Objective: Influence of crystallinity on thermomechanical properties of refractories.	Raw Materials: Tabular Alumina Processing Route: Sintering in shaft kilns. Main Objective: Refractory thermomechanical properties optimisation	Raw Materials: Spherical Alumina Processing Route: Fusion and bubble blowing process Main Objective: Investigating the effects of aggregate shape and processing on castable properties.
7	Molla EWNETE	PIMM/Elkem	Raw Materials: Microsilica Processing Route: Carbothermic reduction of high purity quartz and carbon in electric arc furnace Main Objective: Develop a cement-free refractory castable using microsilica as a green cement-free binder	Raw Materials: AloxX-Spheres Processing Route: High temperature atomization Main Objective: Effect of the shape of alumina fines on thermodynamic properties and H ₂ -corrosion resistance of alumina spinel containing castables	Raw Materials: Calcium aluminat cement Processing Route: CAC is produced by fusing limestone and bauxite together Main Objective: The influence of type and dosage of cement binder on thermomechanical properties
8	Harikeshava RANGANATHAN	IRCER/Imerys	Raw Materials: Alumina - andalusite Processing Route: DEM virtual lab Main Objective: Influences of isotropic – anisotropic interaction on the thermal shock resistance	Raw Materials: Alumina - mullite Processing Route: DEM virtual lab Main Objective: Influences of isotropic - anisotropic interaction on the thermal shock resistance	Raw Materials: Alumina - aluminium titanate Processing Route: DEM virtual lab Main Objective: Influences of isotropic – anisotropic interaction on the thermal shock resistance
9	Michiel SMEDES	MUL/Safran	Raw Materials: Fused Mullite Processing Route: Fusion in an electric arc furnace. Main Objective: Thermal stability of structural ceramics	Raw Materials: Tabular Alumina Processing Route: Sintered α-corundum crystals (Al ₂ O ₃) Main Objective: Mullite formation	Raw Materials: Microsilica Processing Route: Carbothermic reduction of high purity quartz and carbon in electric arc furnace Main Objective: Cement-free binder and mullite formation
10	Paula CAMPOS DE OLIVEIRA	BAM/Safran	Raw Materials: Fused silica Processing Route: Fusion in an electric arc furnace Main Objective: Dimensional stability of ceramic cores	Raw Materials: N/A Processing Route: N/A Main Objective: N/A	Raw Materials: N/A Processing Route: N/A Main Objective: N/A

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